

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE SEVERITY OF RESTORATION OF THE STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL STATE OF THE LIVER LOBE IN DONORS AND RECIPIENTS DURING LIFETIME CLOSELY RELATED TRANSPLANTATION

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Summary. *The purpose of the work was to study markers of cytolysis and cholestasis syndrome in donors and recipients in the dynamics of the early postoperative period after liver transplantation (LT). Under observation were 50 recipients of liver lobes from living-related donors, as well as 50 related donors. Cytolysis syndrome in the postoperative period for donors was resolved by day 5, reaching its peak increase 12 hours after LT. Recipients, however, exhibited specific features: the peak of enzymeemia occurred 24 hours after LT, and the levels of ALT and AST were significantly higher compared to donors ($p < 0.05$). After 5 days, there was a tendency for both AST and ALT levels to increase, indicating ongoing membrane-destructive processes in hepatocytes that require correction. Immediately after the operation, the cholestasis syndrome tended to increase in both donors and recipients. However, the intensity of total bilirubin elevation was 2.1 times higher in recipients compared to donors ($p < 0.05$). Throughout the next observation period, the concentration of total bilirubin in donors was 2.0-1.7 times lower than in recipients, and normalization of the indicator occurred by day 5 for donors, whereas it remained elevated in recipients up to 60 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ for up to 10 days of observation. Discussing the results, it should be noted that the decrease in AST indicates cessation of membranous destruction of subcellular structures of hepatocytes – mitochondria and nuclei, which are the sources of this enzyme. Elevated ALT levels indicate increased permeability of the cytoplasmic membrane, necessitating the use of membrane stabilizers*

Key words: *liver lobe in donors, recipients, lifetime closely related transplantation, cytolysis syndrome, cholestasis syndrome.*

Introduction. Liver transplantation (LT) is the treatment of choice for the treatment of end-stage chronic liver disease (ESLD) [2,3]. Cadaveric whole organ transplantation and liver lobe transplantation from a living related donor differ in a number of features. For cadaveric transplantation, ischemia-reperfusion complications are more common, and with LT, not the entire organ is transplanted from a living donor, but only part of it, which may have implications for the timing of restoration of full liver function in maintaining homeostasis [4,6,7].

Patients with end-stage liver disease – ESLD are characterized by a few syndromes: hepatorenal, hepatopulmonary syndrome, renal failure, the severity of which depends on the etiology of ESLD [5]. In the structure of the pathology that caused ESLD, liver cirrhosis (LC) predominates - up to 70%, fulminant liver necrosis - up to 8%, hepatocellular carcinoma - less than 7%, biliary atresia - up to 3%, primary sclerosing cholangitis - up to 8%, which partly determines the specificity of postoperative complications [2,6].

The initial metabolic status in patients with end-stage liver disease is characterized by varying degrees of severity of dysproteinemia due to a decrease in protein synthetic function of the liver (hypoalbuminemia against the background of hyperglobulinemia), manifestations of cholestasis and cytolysis syndrome, as well as hypocholesterolemia and hyperglycemia due to a decrease in the exchange of glycogen and lipoproteins in the liver [1,5]. Understanding the pathophysiological features of restoration of liver function in the conditions of a healthy donor body during hemihepatectomy and in the conditions of a compromised liver recipient body will allow optimizing tactics in the perioperative period.

The purpose of the work was to study markers of cytolysis and cholestasis syndrome in donors and recipients in the dynamics of the early postoperative period.

Methods. Under observation were 50 recipients of liver lobes from living-related donors, as well as 50 related donors, who received treatment at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Surgery named after Academician V. Vakhidov from August 2022 to December 2023. This group of recipients was selected during the second stage of mastering the LT technique in our Center, four years after the first LT was performed in 2018.

All patients underwent determination of basic metabolic panel parameters, liver profile, and lactate using the fully automated VITROS-5600 biochemical analyzer (USA). Blood serum analysis was conducted immediately at the end of the surgery, at 12 and 24 hours, and on the 5th-7th and 10th-12th days post-surgery.

Results. "Among the studied recipients, there were 21 women (42%) and 29 men (58%). The average age of the patients was 39.2 ± 11.3 years ($M \pm SD$), and the body mass index (BMI) was 23.5 ± 1.5 kg/m². The average Model for End-Stage Liver Disease (MELD) score among recipients was 17.3 ± 3.8 . The average weight of the graft from the donor was 687.7 ± 124.6 g. The graft-to-recipient weight ratio (GRWR) averaged $1.1 \pm 0.3\%$. The 50 donors were related as follows: the majority were siblings (24 donors, 48%), followed by children (12 donors, 24%), nephews/nieces (9 donors, 18%), spouses (3 donors, 6%), and parents (2 donors, 4%). The average age of the donors was 29.1 ± 1.6 years, and their BMI was 22.1 ± 0.65 kg/m². The characteristics of the linear and volumetric parameters of the liver in donors according to contrast-enhanced MSCT were: right lobe volume 749.5 ± 52.0 ml, left lobe volume 522.2 ± 20.1 ml; liver density 81.3 ± 4.8 (min 74.4, max 88.3), arterial blood flow velocity $AF = 33.9 \pm 1.9$ (min 25.5, max 42.2), portal blood flow velocity $PF = 144.4 \pm 8.2$ (min 116.2, max 172.3), and perfusion index $PI = 19.5 \pm 1.4$ (min 14.7, max 24.3)."

All donors had no contraindications to related donation. In the donors' initial metabolic status, no laboratory parameter deviations from the reference interval were detected, whereas the recipients showed signs of liver damage syndromes. In the recipients' initial status, there were moderately expressed signs of cholestasis syndrome in the form of hyperbilirubinemia (an increase in total bilirubin due to the direct fraction ($p < 0.05$)) and elevated levels of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) ($p < 0.05$) and gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) ($p < 0.05$). There was a mild degree of hepatocyte cytolysis with hyperenzymemia of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) less than three times the upper limit of the reference interval ($p < 0.05$). Hepatodepressive syndrome (reduced liver involvement in protein, lipid, and carbohydrate metabolism) manifested as decreased albumin levels ($p < 0.05$), cholesterol ($p < 0.05$), hyperglycemia with low lactate levels as an indicator of low gluconeogenesis intensity in the liver ($p < 0.05$), decreased acetylcholinesterase (AChE), prolonged international normalized ratio (INR)

($p < 0.05$), prolonged prothrombin time (PT) ($p < 0.05$), and impaired transmethylation reactions in the liver, indicated by a decrease in homocysteine concentration (table 1).

Table 1. Baseline Metabolic Status of Donors and Recipients Before Surgery

Parameter	Units of Measurement	Reference Interval	Healthy Liver Donors (Mean,95% CI)	Liver recipients with ESLD (Mean,95% CI)
Age	years	-	29,1(22,1-37,4)	39,2(25,0-55,0)
BMI	kg/m ²	18-24,9	22,1(19,0-28,5)	23,5(18,4-27,8)
Glucose	mmol/L	3,3-6,0	4,9(4,6-5,3)	6,334 (5,05-7,63)*
Total Protein	g/L	64-83	78,1(74,0-84,5)	68,6 (64,3-72,8)
Albumin	g/L	32-52	46,0(40,0-51,0)	30,3 (25,6-35,1)*
Globulins	g/L	26-47	32,1(28,8-40,5)	38,9(37,2-54,0)*
Urea	mmol/L	2,1-7,1	5,75(4,3-6,3)	6,48 (5,02-7,94)
Creatinine	μmol/L	70-110 м, 55-95ж	62,0(53,1-68,8)	59,2 (50,6-67,9)
Sodium	mmol/L	136-145	136,1 (134,0-139,8)	136,1(134,4-137,8)
Potassium	mmol/L	3,5-5,1	4,3 (4,15-4,73)	3,97(3,69-4,26)
Total Bilirubin	μmol/L	1,7-17,5	13,2(7,8-18,5)	51,86(30,05-73,67)*
Direct Bilirubin	μmol/L	0-5	0,5(0,3-1,7)	7,81(2,43-16,47)*
ALT	U/L	15-45	24,8(18,0-34,8)	59,9(40,4-79,5)*
AST	U/L	11-66	27,5(24,2-31,6)	81,1(49,6-112,6)*
ALP	U/L	38-126	64,0(38,5-104,3)	106,3(87,1-125,5)*
GGT	U/L	12-73	25,6(12,6-50,5)	51,2(38,1-64,3)*
AChE	U/L	4650-12220	5790 (3489-9630)	2005(238-3773)*
Amylase	U/L	30-110	80,1(69,9-90,4)	69,4(59,5-79,4)
Total Cholesterol	mmol/L	3,0-5,2	4,0(3,33-4,98)	3,1(2,4-3,6)*
Triglycerides	mmol/L	0,45-1,7	0,9(0,6-1,3)	1,12(0,81-1,44)
Lactate	mmol/L	1,3-3,3	1,76(1,52-1,88)	0,51(0,34-0,81)*
Homocysteine	mmol/L	4,1-11,1	6,96(5,9-8,0)	2,64(1,62-3,67)

*- statistically significant compared to healthy donors at $p < 0.05$

In the postoperative period, the cytolysis syndrome in donors resolved earlier than in recipients, and the levels of ALT and AST enzyme activity from day 1 to 10 post-transplantation were significantly lower in donors compared to recipients ($p < 0.05$). Immediately after transplantation, both ALT and AST levels increased similarly in donors and recipients, as there were no statistically significant differences between the donor and recipient groups for these parameters during this period ($p > 0.05$). Subsequently, the dynamics of AST and ALT in donors after hemihepatectomy and in recipients of liver lobes differed. The peak increase in AST occurred immediately after the end of the operation in donors, while ALT peaked at 12 hours postoperatively, showing an 8.7-fold increase from baseline ($p < 0.05$). By day 5 postoperative period, AST activity in donors returned to within the reference interval, while elevated ALT levels persisted for up to 10 days of observation.

In liver lobe recipients, the ALT dynamics showed a peak increase at 24 hours post-transplantation, followed by a decrease by day 5. Overall, the ALT dynamics were positive, as stabilization of the indicator was observed by day 10, although its level was 2.1 times higher than that of donors, indicating the effectiveness of membrane-stabilizing and antioxidant therapy. The peak increase in AST among recipients occurred earlier than ALT, at 12 hours post-transplantation, and thereafter AST activity decreased by the end of day 1, remaining 1.3 times

higher than in donors by day 5. Starting from day 5, AST levels in donors were within the reference interval, while mild ALT enzyme activity persisted until day 10. In recipients, there was a tendency for both AST and ALT levels to increase starting from day 5, indicating ongoing membrane-destructive processes in hepatocytes requiring correction. Cholestasis syndrome post-transplantation tended to increase in both donors and recipients, but the intensity of total bilirubin elevation in recipients was 2.1 times higher than in donors immediately after the surgery.

At other observation points, the total bilirubin concentration in donors was 2.0-1.7 times lower than in recipients, with normalization occurring in donors by day 5, whereas in recipients it remained elevated up to 60 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ on days 5 and 10 of observation. Notably, the dynamics of bilirubinemia were variable in recipients after 5 days of observation: by day 10, 8% of cases experienced an increase in total bilirubin above 100 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ due to biliary complications; in 5 patients, the total bilirubin level decreased to the reference interval and was 19-21 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, while in the remaining patients it ranged from 30-80 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, which is reflected in the 95% confidence interval for this indicator - 95% CI: 31.2-89.3 $\mu\text{mol/L}$.

Direct bilirubin in donors remained within the reference interval at all observation points, whereas in recipients it tended to increase after the first day. For recipients, the 95% confidence interval (CI) for direct bilirubin on days 1, 5, and 10 of observation was 2.66-16.6 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, 5.74-21.8 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, and 0.4-36.2 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, respectively, indicating a wide range of changes depending on the development of localized bile collections and other biliary complications (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Dynamics of Cholestasis Syndrome in Donors and Recipients

The dynamics of the cholestasis marker ALP in recipients and donors were similar up to day 5. By day 10, ALP levels in recipients increased on average to 138 (95% CI: 66.3-209.7) U/L, which was also associated with bile outflow obstruction. In donors, after hemihepatectomy, ALP activity remained within the reference interval at all observation points, indicating a compensatory state of the remaining left liver lobe.

GGT activity in donors increased by day 5, exceeding the reference interval, but returned to the normal range by day 10. In recipients, GGT activity progressively increased by days 10-12, reaching 203 (95% CI: 29.4-377.4) U/L by day 10.

Discussion. Discussing the results, it should be noted that the decrease in AST indicates cessation of membranous destruction of subcellular structures of hepatocytes – mitochondria and nuclei, which are the sources of this enzyme. Positive dynamics of AST suggests intact mitochondrial membranes and energetic metabolism of hepatocytes, cessation of their death, and a favorable prognosis; elevated AST serves as a marker of irreversible changes in cells, primarily in hepatocytes. Elevated ALT levels indicate increased permeability of the cytoplasmic membrane, necessitating the use of membrane stabilizers. Vitamin E and essential phospholipids can be among the most effective membrane stabilizers, with succinate can be as a metabotropic agent.

We associate the dynamics of GGT in recipients with increased drug load and enhanced hepatic biotransformation, as well as potential subcellular structure destruction of hepatocytes, particularly the endoplasmic reticulum (ER). Considering that GGT is predominantly located in the membranes of the biliary pole of hepatocytes and in cells of bile ducts, and its activity is high in membranes of cells with high secretory and absorptive capacity (bile duct epithelium, proximal renal tubules, acinar part of the pancreas, brush border of enterocytes), changes in GGT activity reflect disturbances occurring in both the liver and other tissues. Moreover, GGT is more sensitive to changes in hepatocytes (membrane destruction, detoxification activation) than ALT, AST, ALP, and LDH, and it has a short half-life (9-20 hours).

Therefore, it can serve as a good marker of bile excretory function in liver graft recipients. It is important to consider that the increase in GGT may be associated not only with enhanced enzyme synthesis due to drug stimulation but also with cell membrane damage caused by endotoxins and reactive oxygen species (ROS) due to ischemia-reperfusion, infection, as well as detergent action of surfactants - bile acids, which promote the release of GGT from ER membranes in all types of cholestasis. Thus, we attribute the elevation of GGT in recipients to three factors: enzyme activation by xenobiotics, cholestasis, and ischemia in bile ducts.

Conclusions.

1. In the initial metabolic status of the recipients, there were signs of liver damage syndromes (cytolysis, cholestasis, hepatargy), while the donors did not exhibit these signs.
2. Cytolysis syndrome in the postoperative period for donors was resolved by day 5, reaching its peak increase 12 hours after liver transplantation (LT). Recipients, however, exhibited specific features: the peak of enzymeemia occurred 24 hours after LT, and the levels of ALT and AST enzymeemia were significantly higher compared to donors ($p < 0.05$). After 5 days, there was a tendency for both AST and ALT levels to increase, indicating ongoing membrane-destructive processes in hepatocytes that require correction.
3. Immediately after the operation, the cholestasis syndrome tended to increase in both donors and recipients. However, the intensity of total bilirubin elevation was 2.1 times higher in recipients compared to donors ($p < 0.05$). Throughout the next observation period, the concentration of total bilirubin in donors was 2.0-1.7 times lower than in recipients, and

normalization of the indicator occurred by day 5 for donors, whereas it remained elevated in recipients up to 60 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ for up to 10 days of observation.

4. The dynamics of the cholestasis marker ALP in recipients and donors were consistent up to 5 days post-operation. By day 10, recipients showed an increase in ALP levels to an average of 138 U/L (95% CI: 66.3-209.7), whereas donors who underwent hemihepatectomy maintained ALP activity within the reference range throughout the observation period. This indicates compensated state of the remaining left lobe of the liver in donors.
5. GT activity in donors increased and exceeded the reference interval by day 5 post-operation, returning to normal values by day 10. In contrast, GGT activity in recipients continued to rise progressively, reaching 203 U/L (95% CI: 29.4-377.4) by day 10-12. We attribute this increase to three factors: enzyme activation by xenobiotics, cholestasis, and ischemia in bile ducts.

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